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QUALITY OF EDUCATION IS THE QUALITY OF LIFE

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Abstract: *The article provides a brief definition of education in the era of globalization, highlighting the role of education quality. It emphasizes that the ecological, socio-political, and economic problems and crises arising during globalization, as well as their solutions, are linked to the quality of education. The quality of education is presented as a key criterion for determining the quality of life. The article discusses thoughts and solutions on how to ensure and adapt the quality of education and upbringing to align with the spirit of the times in today's globalized and information-driven society.*

Key terms: *globalization process, education and upbringing, education quality, intellectual wealth, quality of life.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, the 21st century is characterized as the era of advanced technologies, the age of intellect, the age of comprehensive information dissemination, and the era of globalization. The term "globalization" was first introduced by American scholar T. Levitt in an article published in the "Harvard Business Review" in 1983. The author used this term to describe the process of the unification of various markets for products produced by large transnational corporations. However, in the current context, globalization carries different meanings and significance.

Globalization is a universal process created as a result of human consciousness and thinking. It is a continuous and evolving transition to an information-based society that knows no borders and regions and recognizes no system. In such a society, human thinking has a leading position. Thought acts as a window reflecting the level of development of society, revealing achievements and shortcomings. It is no secret that the value and perfection of a person is determined by the level of thinking and intelligence. Information is the main factor affecting the formation of thinking and cognitive abilities of a person.[2]. Consequently, the development of modern civilized society is characterized by the process of information dissemination and determined by its intellectual potential. The source of intellectual wealth and potential, the main factor of its development is the quality of the education and training process.[3]

RESEARCH METHODS

In the research process, the following methods were utilized: analysis of scientific and educational literature, pedagogical observation, comparative analysis, generalization, pedagogical experiment, and foresight methods.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The ecological, socio-political, and economic problems and crises arising in the era of globalization are shaped and developed in relation to the quality of education. Education is a vital sector of social life. It is education that shapes the intellectual, cultural, and moral level of society. Today, the strength and power of any state, its level of development, and the social-political environment are defined by its intellectual potential. The growth of intellectual potential is primarily assessed through the quality of education.

From the above statements, one might ask:

Why does the quality of education impact all vital activities of humanity?

First, humanity has reached a level of global interconnection in all areas, including the education system. Today, the problems of a single state or nation can significantly affect global development. The solutions to emerging ecological, economic, and political problems and crises require a commitment to intellectual and moral development in the future. This can only be achieved by establishing a proper and quality education system.

Second, the primary focus of education ultimately leads to upbringing. Upbringing is an extremely important, complex, and urgent issue that has been and will continue to be a significant concern. Abdulla Avloni's book "Turkiy Guliston yoki axloq" (*Turkish Gulistan or morality*) contains important thoughts in the chapter "The Time of Upbringing." He states: "It is now clear that upbringing should begin from the day of birth, strengthening our existence, illuminating our thoughts, beautifying our morals, and clarifying our intellect. One may ask, who is responsible for this upbringing and where does it take place? To this, we can answer: first, family upbringing, which is the mother's duty; second, school and madrasa upbringing, which is the responsibility of the father, teacher, educator, and government."

It is precisely this school and madrasa upbringing that has been carried out by teachers and educators in the past and continues to be so today. In our view, the influence of the environment plays a significant role in upbringing. Children tend to imitate not what they hear or read the most, but what they see. Well, can we be role models for children in terms of upbringing? What are children learning from us? What role does information on the global Internet play in education? Are children posting information that negatively affects their upbringing, or is it adults? Perhaps we should start our education and upbringing from ourselves.

In other words, for education and upbringing to be of high quality, we (educators) must first be worthy of providing quality education. Thirdly, all vital human relationships (politics, economics, social relations, etc.) are shaped and developed based on interconnections and mutual influences among people. The level of these relationships, particularly political and economic relations, will certainly change in relation to the quality of education.

From the above, we can conclude that the root of all the problems currently arising in the world lies in the quality deficiencies of the education and upbringing system. It would not be incorrect to assert that all issues can only be resolved through a high level of consciousness, correct thinking, exceptional knowledge, and high moral and ethical standards.

The solution lies in increasing attention to education and upbringing, allocating more resources to this sector, and improving the quality of education. However, it is important to emphasize that the positive outcomes of reforms in education are also dependent on how well educators understand the essence and significance of the education system in a globalized and information-driven society and how sincerely they implement these reforms.

How can we ensure the quality of education and upbringing in the current globalized and information-driven society, and how can we adapt it to the spirit of the times?

First and foremost, it is essential to develop an entirely new system for ensuring the quality of education and upbringing that takes into account the opportunities provided by global internet access, distance learning, and international educational standards. Currently, the content of education is often focused on achieving high economic efficiency in production and fully satisfying individual personal interests. In some cases, this leads to a search for ways to obtain maximum economic benefit from any knowledge base.

Despite our efforts to nurture our children with a strong moral foundation, an environment based on self-interest can pose challenges. Every parent desires their child to be as good as anyone else, prioritizing higher education and securing a well-paying job. However, the education and upbringing process should primarily serve to cultivate and develop human morality at a high level.

The education and upbringing system must not only meet humanity's material and spiritual interests but also contribute to the purification of its spirit, faith, will, and conscience, as well as the formation of genuine human emotions. Learning and acquiring knowledge should become a daily necessity for every individual, akin to other daily needs such as washing, dressing, and eating.

The main directions for ensuring the quality of education include the extensive use of modern information and communication technologies and innovative pedagogical technologies in the educational process. The consistent development of information and communication technologies today necessitates that the education system meets the requirements of the global educational environment. The use of information and telecommunications technologies in education has facilitated the emergence of distance learning and has laid the foundation for the education process to transform into an international one.

As emphasized above, the implementation of innovative pedagogical technologies in the educational process also plays a crucial role in the establishment of such an education system.

From the above, several questions arise:

- What are the main components of the quality of education and the criteria that define it?
- Why is it recognized today that “the quality of education equals the quality of life”?
- What role do modern information and pedagogical technologies play in enhancing the quality of education?
- What methods are appropriate for ensuring the quality of education in the current era of information technologies?
- What is the essence of modern pedagogical technologies and teaching methods?

The questions above represent the main criteria defining the quality of education, and each one necessitates scientific research in specific directions.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be emphasized that the quality of education and upbringing is a highly important, problematic, and urgent issue today. This is because all other social issues, political problems, and economic indicators develop directly in relation to the level of education quality. Moreover, the quality of education determines the fate of the state and society, as well as the destiny of all humanity. Therefore, it is not incorrect to interpret education quality as equivalent to life quality.

Improving the quality of education is an expansive domain. Consequently, accurately assessing the dynamics of education quality growth, clearly defining its criteria, and forecasting and planning future education quality indicators are extremely important and pressing matters.

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